

MODEL OF SPEECH SKILLS FORMATION IN TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the model of formation of speech skills of teachers was considered. Forming the spiritual culture of modern teachers at school, becoming a highly qualified teacher, skilled pedagogue and effective scientist is one of the most important pedagogical problems.

The current state of Uzbek education leads us to understand the urgent need to change the semantic emphasis of teaching. The training of a future specialist is determined to a large extent by the educational paradigm available at the university, the level of qualifications of professors and teachers.

Established educational practices aimed at imparting the maximum amount of knowledge, sometimes neglecting the spiritual and moral foundations of human formation and development, limit the formation of human individuality, which leads to socio-cultural and personal identity. leads to a crisis.

In this regard, it is very important to understand the university as a socio-cultural system, whose functions are not limited to training a person for professional activity. It should be considered as a form of translation and reproduction of cultural norms, values, ideas, a space where social ideology is formed.

The concept of modernization of education envisages formation of speech skills in teachers - development and testing of models for reforming its organization, structure and content.

Thus, the priorities of personnel policy at the state level are determined:

- development of professional development programs by teachers of higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan that correspond to the structure, content and requirements of international professional-pedagogical associations;
- to improve the system of training university, college and school teachers and improve their qualifications, to ensure continuity in the development of the culture, scientific and methodological experience and professional competence of the academic community of Uzbekistan;
- formation of a wide (by region) network of institutes for improving the qualifications of scientific and pedagogical personnel, faculties and centers for improving the level of pedagogical skills;

- development and implementation of an effective system of post-higher vocational education by concentrating network resources in higher educational institutions with prestigious scientific and scientific-pedagogical schools.

The need to reform the personnel retraining system is not only to "provide and form knowledge", but also to educate a new class of teachers who can be active culture creators. For an objective and complete description of a modern teacher, we form the most important criteria for his professional activity. Of course, it should be a first-class specialist, a highly qualified teacher, a skilled pedagogue and an effective scientist.

The level of professional skill of the teacher is largely determined by the level of skill of the teacher. In the context of the "national education doctrine", there is a trend indicating the need for "compulsory language education and personality education". Language, as a powerful tool that regulates people's activities in various fields, is a criterion of speech behavior of a modern person. It is an important and urgent task of modern education to understand how a person owns language wealth and how efficiently he uses it. Knowing the literary language is especially important for a teacher whose professional activity is based on speech competence.

Important indicators of a teacher's teaching skills include:

- scientific and informative presentation;
- evidence and comments;
- sequence of questions;
- methodological development of the material;
- focus clearly on the problem;
- use of the principle of appearance;
- combining the presentation with the presentation of audiovisual materials;
- availability of the material provided for the given student contingent;
- clarification of all newly introduced concepts and terms.

All these criteria are reflected in the main communicative qualities of speech (content, clarity, logic, comprehensibility, expressiveness, emotionality, etc.). An indispensable condition for the successful work of a teacher is the high culture of his oral and written speech. The correct, emotional, communicative and appropriate speech of the teacher allows him to effectively influence the thoughts and feelings of the student, to educate a well-rounded person. The more qualified the teacher, the more demanding he is about his speech, the more acutely he understands how important it is in his professional activity.

A comprehensive review of the characteristics of speech allows to determine the criteria of the teacher's professional speech culture and determine ways to improve it:

1. Mandatory knowledge of current literary language standards and their use in oral and written speech.
2. To have terminological culture.
3. The ability to organize and conduct a dialogue using various questions.
4. Having pedagogically oriented rules of etiquette.
5. Using basic technological and practical knowledge of speech technology.

The problem of teacher speech culture is being solved within the framework of the new concept of professional development of professors and teachers developed at the scientific research institute. Training institutes, as the main link of the educational

improvement system, should help to change the teacher's position on the development of professional speech, recognize the need for continuous purposeful work on the selection and understanding of their speech activity in general, speech on the basis of tools appropriate to a particular educational and speech situation.

Taking into account the social order of the society, purposeful and systematic work on training the teacher in speech culture is envisaged in the system of retraining of personnel under the National Research Institute. It seems to us that for all types of course work in the professional development system, certain hours should be allocated to improve the speech culture of the teacher.

It is necessary to distinguish the problem of the teacher's speech culture into a separate block in the content of professional development courses, to include it in the curriculum of retraining courses, to reveal its essence and direction.

The course "Teacher's speech culture" is aimed at improving the teacher's speech skills, and has determined the content and methodology of the course, which is called the study of the state of teachers' speech culture.

The course program is intended for teachers of all specialties. It has a clearly defined professional and speech direction: its purpose is to teach the culture of speech communication, to form a terminologically clear and expressive speech.

Accordingly, the main objectives of the course are:

- the need to form a correct understanding of the term "teacher's speech culture" among students, to determine its content;
- identifying typical deficiencies in the field of speech culture among course participants;
- getting to know the basics of speech activity, standards of modern Uzbek literary language, qualities of "good" speech;
- review of the basics of "academic" speech, systematization of knowledge about the structure of speech, methods of presenting material, methods of attracting attention;
- acquaintance with the main educational and scientific genres;
- to equip listeners with a complex methodology that allows them to independently improve speech culture in the future;
- getting acquainted with modern theoretical and methodological literature on speech culture, speech technology, speech etiquette;
- formation of the need to further improve their speech culture.

The course of teacher speech culture includes the following components: purposeful, stimulating and motivational, meaningful, prompt and active, control and adjustment, evaluative and effective.

1. Target component:

- teaching methods for creating effective, appropriate, harmonious speech, developing professional speech competence, training a strong linguistic personality.

2. Stimulating and motivational component:

- practical orientation of the lesson, student orientation to the educational process, creation of conditions for the realization of communicative and emotional-personal aspirations of teachers.

3. Content component:

- scientifically based amount of knowledge, skills and qualifications specified in the training plans and training manuals for this course.

4. Operational and activity component:

- methods, methods and system of educational tools, forms of organization of educational time and space.

5. Control and adjustment component:

- individual and group presentations, written work, independent and creative work, test, tests.

6. Evaluative and effective component:

- evaluation by the teacher, course participants, self-evaluation; determining the compliance of the results with the set goals and tasks, determining the causes of the deficiencies found and the ways to fill them.

The model of formation of speech skills in teachers can be called:

☑ theoretical knowledge necessary for a teacher;

☑ appropriate speech environment;

☑ choosing and using effective teaching methods and methods;

☑ the teacher's belief in the practical value of the knowledge he has received.

In the practice of conducting the course, students note important professional tasks for a teacher in any specialty:

1) thoroughly prepare for each lesson, analyze one's own speech, if possible, prevent speech errors, refer to dictionaries and reference books in case of difficulties;

2) show students the correctness and literacy of designing all types of writing (on the blackboard, reviewing term papers, theses, etc.);

3) assessment of written work of students in any subject, taking into account language literacy;

4) forming the ability to analyze, compare, argue, generalize;

5) to improve the skills of independent work with books (composing abstracts, synopses, comments, reviews, reviews), to develop the skills of working with additional literature (dictionaries, reference books, encyclopedias);

6) getting used to systematic work with the terminological dictionary, forming the skills of pronouncing and writing difficult words;

7) to treat students' oral speech with care, to form their conscious attitude to the beauty of the Uzbek word, the riches of the Uzbek language;

8) to create a cultural language environment in the classroom, an environment of rejection of negative speech and language phenomena (negligence of speech, illiteracy, vulgarism, slang, etc.).

9) education of the culture of speech communication in the classroom, prevention of rudeness and insolence towards classmates and teachers;

10) consulting with students and readers on issues related to modern literary language norms.

The implementation of such tasks directly depends on the level of speech culture of the modern teacher and the entire pedagogical team.

Most likely, only a pedagogical team that understands the seriousness of the problem and is psychologically, theoretically and methodologically prepared can do such work. The

following system of evaluation criteria was used for the "Culture of teacher's speech" course: highly scientific and practical; compliance with the standards of modern literary language; professional direction; the ability to develop topics at a creative level; compliance with real curricula and programs to the complexity of the subject of the course.

One of the ways to improve the qualifications of professors and teachers in the conditions of a higher educational institution is to organize a permanent seminar dedicated to the problem of the formation of the teacher's speech culture. Teachers can also meet their needs for improving speech culture in weekly, two-week, one-year professional retraining courses on the specialty "Teachers' Speech Culture". The practice of conducting such a course in the system of professional development in Uzbekistan shows that solving the problems of increasing and developing the personnel potential of higher education allows not only the implementation of current and prospective tasks. Education workers, but at the same time contribute to the achievement of strategic goals of modernization of Uzbek education. Thus, the search for new approaches, conceptual methods and meaningful forms in the system of training under the national research institute helps to increase the professional level of teachers and forms a highly qualified faculty.

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